

Study of Ligature Marks in Asphyxial Deaths

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Received: 25-08-2024 / Revised: 23-09-2024 / Accepted: 25-10-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: The ligature mark in case of asphyxia death is an important part in the investigation. The correlation of external and internal findings helps to identify the different facts in case. The purpose of this research is to study the ligature marks in asphyxial deaths.

Method: The observational descriptive study was conducted in the Department of Forensic Medicine and Toxicology, The Oxford Medical College and Research Centre, Bangalore to study the ligature marks in asphyxia deaths among 100 autopsy cases received during the time period of one year. The details about the victims regarding the circumstances of death, type of ligature material, manner and apparent cause of death was recorded. Results were analyzed using SPSS version 25.0.

Results: Out of all the age groups maximum cases were in the group of 21 to 30 years (38%) and 31 to 40 years (25%). 66% cases were male and 34% were female. The cause of death in most cases was due to hanging (a) complete (52%) (b) partial (32%) and strangulation (16%). Encircling of mark around the neck was complete in 68% cases and incomplete in 32% of cases. Level of mark at neck was above the level of thyroid-cartilage in 68% cases, at the level in 23% cases and below the level in 9% cases. Direction of marks was oblique in 94% cases and transverse in 6% cases. Deep impression was found in 49% cases, prominent in 45% cases and faint in 6% cases. Continuous marks were found in 95% cases and intermittent in 5% cases. Parchmentization was present in 94% cases and absent in 6% cases.

Conclusion: The results emphasise the significance of a thorough post-mortem examination in uncovering the intricacies underlying these unfortunate events, providing guidance to forensic specialists and judicial authorities in making precise conclusions.

Keywords: Asphyxia, Death, Ligature, Marks, Post-Mortem.

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Introduction

Asphyxia refers to situations when the delivery of oxygen to the blood and tissues is significantly lowered below the usual level due to any obstruction of respiration. In the field of forensic medicine, the term "asphyxia" specifically refers to instances where oxygen deprivation occurs due to physical obstruction of the respiratory system. [1]

Violent asphyxiation is a primary factor contributing to atypical fatalities. Forensic professionals regularly conduct autopsies as part of their work and frequently encounter cases of death resulting from hanging and other forms of strangling. [2-4] Suicide is a grave matter that significantly affects both public health and the economy on a global scale. An indicator commonly associated with death by hanging or strangulation is the presence of a ligature mark around the victim's neck. [5]

Ligature induces the formation of a furrow or groove in the tissue, which initially appears pale, then changes to a yellow or yellowish brown colour, and eventually becomes dry. The tissue will have a firm texture and appear like parchment due to the drying out of the somewhat abraded skin. Over time, the groove becomes desiccated and assumes a grey hue. The classification of a ligature mark is contingent upon the composition, positioning, and duration of suspension of the deceased corpse. The visibility of the ligature mark is enhanced when the material is rigid and the ligature is slender. Under specific circumstances, the mark may be absent if the ligature material is pliable and promptly removed following the individual's demise. [6] Usually, there is simply a single ligature mark. Alternatively, spiral twists, several rotations around the neck, or upward movement of material caused by a fall can also lead to the creation of many imprints. The mark is

frequently slanted in position and situated above the thyroid cartilage, between the larynx and chin. The mark in the rear is unfinished, displaying an imprecise imprint of the knot where it is usually suspended, commonly at the mastoid process on one side. It is orientated in an upward direction and runs parallel to the mandibular line. [7]

Hanging is a way of inducing death by suspending the body with a rope around the neck. The body weight, or a fraction thereof, serves as a constriction. [8] Strangulation refers to the act of constricting the victim's neck using ligature material or any other means in order to obstruct the flow of air between the atmosphere and the lungs. The act is performed without the need to suspend the victim's body, and the pressure applied on the neck is exerted externally (originating from outside) rather than being caused by the victim's own weight or head. In cases of ligature strangulation, the ligature material is tightly tied around the neck using a secure knot. [9]

Any object that has been used as a ligature and is now within reach can be utilised as ligature material in hanging. Occasionally, a basic loop is utilised, but more commonly, a single knot is employed to form a running noose or secured with a granny or reef knot. The mark can exhibit numerous twists around the neck and/or various knots, contributing to a similar degree of intricacy. [10]

Understanding ligature signs in cases of asphyxia not only improve forensic processes but also provide valuable information for preventative actions. This knowledge is crucial in the quest of justice and the development of comprehensive programs to reduce these incidents. The purpose of this research is to study the ligature marks in asphyxial deaths.

Material and Methods

The observational descriptive study was conducted in the Department of Forensic Medicine and Toxicology, The Oxford Medical College and Research Centre, Bangalore to study the ligature marks in asphyxia deaths among autopsy cases

received during the time period of one year. Ethical permission was taken from institutional ethics committee before commencement of study. Relative of subjects were asked to sign an informed consent for documentations purposes.

Consecutive sampling was done and 100 autopsy cases received due to asphyxia in the department were selected on the basis of eligibility criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Asphyxia cases occurred by mechanical interference with respiration.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Cases of birth asphyxia in neonates
2. Cases showing signs of decomposition masking findings of asphyxia.

The details about the victims regarding the circumstances of death, type of ligature material, manner and apparent cause of death was recorded from police requisition letter and inquest (Panchanama) report. A hand lens examination of the neck was performed to correlate the findings of the ligature mark with respect to substance, impression, pattern, colour, kind of knot, degree of ligature, and skin changes, among other factors. The body was opened using a Y-shaped incision, and the neck dissection was finished layer by layer. A part of the skin and subcutaneous tissue from the ligature mark was removed and stored in 10% formalin for histological analysis. All physical findings were recorded.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive and inferential statistics was performed accordingly by using IBM SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) Statistics for Windows, version 25 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY). A *P*-value of less than 0.05 will be used to indicate significant results.

Results

Out of all the age groups maximum cases were in the group of 21 to 30 years (38%) and 31 to 40 years (25%). 66% cases were male and 34% were female as shown in table 1.

Table 1: Demographic data of cases

Demographic data	Percentage	
Age (years)	0-10	0
	11-20	10
	21-30	38
	31-40	25
	41-50	5
	51-60	11
	61-70	4
	71-80	3
	81-90	4
Gender	Male	66
	Female	34

The cause of death in most cases was due to hanging (a) complete (52%) (b) partial (32%) and strangulation (16%) as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1 Distribution of cases on the basis of cause of death

The different type of ligature material used are rope (40%), dupatta (32%), saree (10%), bedsheet (7%), lungi (5%),m plastic water pipe (3%) and band of thread (1%) as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 Type of ligature material used

Encircling of mark around the neck was complete in 68% cases and incomplete in 32% of cases. Level of mark at neck was above the level of thyroid-cartilage in 68% cases, at the level in 23% cases and below the level in 9% cases. Direction of marks was oblique in 94% cases and transverse in

6% cases. Deep impression was found in 49% cases, prominent in 45% cases and faint in 6% cases. Continuous marks were found in 95% cases and intermittent in 5% cases. Parchmentization was present in 94% cases and absent in 6% cases as shown in table 2.

Table 2 Particulars of ligature marks

Particulars of ligature marks	Percentage	
Encircling of mark around the neck	Complete	68
	Incomplete	32
Level of mark at neck	Above the level of thyroid cartilage	68
	At the level of thyroid cartilage	23
	Below the level of thyroid cartilage	9

Direction	Oblique	94
	Transverse	6
Impression	Faint	6
	Prominent	45
	Deep	49
Continuity	Continuous	95
	Intermittent	5
Parchmentization	Present	94
	Absent	6

Position of not was posterior in 6 cases, right side in 60 cases, left side in 33 cases and n chin in 1 case as shown in figure 3.

Figure 3 Position of knot of ligature

Discussion

Distinguishing the physical characteristics of vitality is essential in establishing whether a lesion occurred during life or after death. When there is uncertainty between a homicidal death and a suicidal death, it becomes challenging to establish all the criteria related to vitality within a broader framework. Distinguishing between entire hanging and partial hanging, strangulation, and throttling can be challenging and unclear, particularly in uncommon cases. The forensic pathologist's ability to make a definitive diagnosis is often compromised due to the requirement for immediate on-site investigation and the initial outward assessment of the deceased body. Frequently, the initial incorrect interpretation of the facts is influenced by atypical circumstances, and a divergent diagnostic diagnosis is disregarded. Thus, the cooperation among diverse experts continues to be intricate and important. [11]

A ligature mark can be caused by localized skin damage on the neck due to pressure, often accompanied by lateral friction, which can lead to abrasion. The ligature mark on the neck is of vital diagnostic significance and necessitates thorough examination in terms of its trajectory, depth, and width. Occasionally, the groove preserves the configuration of the ligature material, such as a

helical arrangement of the rope. Conversely, the analysis of the ligature material is an essential component of the autopsy. [12,13]

It was found that the majority of the victims—were between the ages of 21 and 30 and there was male predominance. The current investigation aligns with research conducted by Luck JL et al., Davidson A et al., and Elfawal MA et al, Cooke Ct et al and Dixit PG et al. [14–18]

In our study most of the deaths were due to complete or incomplete hanging. The incidence of hanging deaths has been reported in a number of studies to be 8.97% (Saini OP et al.) and 1.2% (Joshi R et al.). However, a small number of studies, including 11.8% (Talukder MA et al.), do not agree. This could be because the studies are conducted in different regions with different demographics and living styles. [19-23]

Most of the ligature marks were above the thyroid cartilage (68%) in our study. In the study done by Bhosle SH et al, Dinesh Rao and Rajeev Sharma et al, it was seen that the position of ligature mark was above the thyroid cartilage in 70 cases (83.3%), 218 cases(82.58%) and 69.23% cases respectively, a pattern consistent with the pattern observed in our study. [24-26] In hanging the ligature mark was normally situated higher in the

neck above laryngeal prominence. The position of mark in hanging depends on the way - the device was fixed and the suspension point. [27]

In 94% of the instances in our analysis, an obliquely placed ligature mark was found. Our results agreed with those of previous research. [24–28] According to authors, the hanging mark is located obliquely over the neck's circumference. The resultant mark may be horizontal in cases when the suspension point is low because the draw on the rope is almost perpendicular to the body's axis.

Continuous marks were found in 95% cases and intermittent in 5% cases. Parchmentization was present in 94% cases and absent in 6% cases. The colour of the ligature mark depends primarily on the length of time the body was suspended, the type of ligature material used, the time between death and autopsy, and other factors. In the study by Sunil Kumar Sharma GA et al, [1] the ligature mark was reddish brown in colour in 41.7% of cases, parchmentized in 36.7% of cases, and pale in 21.7% of cases. Conversely, in a study by Bharath Kumar Guntheti et al.,[28] the ligature mark was reddish brown in 56.25% of cases, pale in 6.25% of cases, and parchmentized in 37.5% of cases.

Despite making a significant contribution to the field of forensic literature, this study has many drawbacks. Despite being sizable, the sample size might not adequately reflect the variation amongst cases. Furthermore, relying just on information from autopsies and associated sources may miss important confounding variables, making a multidisciplinary approach necessary for a comprehensive understanding of each case.

Conclusion

Ultimately, this study, which is based on autopsies of asphyxial deaths, makes a substantial contribution to the forensic comprehension of these unfortunate occurrences. Examining postmortem discoveries, the peculiarities of ligature marks, and related elements enhances the field of forensic pathology. As the medical-legal community faces the challenges of understanding asphyxial deaths, studies like this one provide valuable information for thorough investigations, strong legal processes, and ultimately, the quest of justice.

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